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TOLERANCE AS A VALUE COMPETENT OF POLYCULTURAL COMPETENT OF THE MODERN TEACHER OF HUMANITE

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У статті йдеться про толерантність як складник ключових компетентностей учителя-словесника при підготовці до викладання в сучасній школі. Наведено практичні результати проведених семінарів та тренінгів, опитувань та анкетувань студентів. Виокремлено основні напрями та етапи формування толерантного ставлення до оточуючих, охарактеризовано поняття толерантність як у загальному розумінні (ослаблення чи відсутність можливості реакції на який-небудь несприятливий чинник унаслідок зниження чутливості до його впливу), так і на індивідуальному рівні.

Толерантність як цінність розкривається автором через ставлення до способу життя інших, їхньої поведінки, звичаїв, почуттів, ідей, вірувань, як умова стабільності та єдності суспільств, особливо тих, які не є гомогенними ні у релігійному, ні в етнічному, ні в інших соціальних вимірах.

Ключові слова: толерантність, розуміння, емпатія, цінність.

It is a common view that a tolerant person accepts diversity and doesn't prejudge others on the basis of religion, race, or gender. If we are to live in harmony with others and seek cooperative solutions to conflicts, we need to focus more on our common humanity than on our differences. Tolerance also involves being flexible and accepting that others have the right to be who they are

Based on dictionary materials tolerance (from the Latin. Tolerantia – patience) in the general sense is weakening or absence of possible reactions to any adverse factors as a result of reduction of sensitivity to its effects. At the individual level it is the ability to take opinions that differ from their own, and the behavior and lifestyles of others without aggression. Tolerance for others' way of life, behavior, customs, feelings, ideas and beliefs is a condition of stability and cohesion of societies, especially those that are not homogeneous either in religious or ethnic or other social dimensions [19].

The workshop was carried out as a survey for students, masters, postgraduate students of Poltava V.G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University (208 people) on the understanding of the tolerance of the individual. To the question «What are the main features of a tolerant person?» were received the following answers: mercy (52.0%); empathy (52.0%); respect (83.3%); humanism (73.4%); responsibility (51.0%); reflection (69.0%); self-regulation (48.9%); tolerance (85.8%). In this article we are going to present our project outlines and the main results.

The program of formation and development of tolerance of students' and pupils' youth. The program of development of tolerance of students' and pupils' youth was created. The *objective* of the program is formation and development of tolerance of students' and pupils' (high school students) youth. *Program task* – is the formation and development of indicators of tolerance: personal responsibility; empathy; constructive interaction with others and the natural environment.

The program involves the creation of a special educational environment with the following *characteristics*: a) setting on the cognitive component tolerance (personal responsibility); b) setting on the emotional component (empathy); c) the formation and development of the behavioral component based on constructive interaction with others and the natural environment.

Unit №1. «The formation and development of positive thinking ecopsychological, internalization of human values and understanding of the values of other cultures.» *Unit №2.* «The formation and development of psychological stability, self-control». *Unit №3.* «Gaining experience of constructive dialogue, friendly and tolerant attitude towards others and the surrounding events that do not violate human rights». The content of the program units is presented by:

1. Mini-lecture, discussion, story.

Mini-lectures are different from full-length lectures because they have significantly shorter duration. Usually mini-lectures don't last more than 10-15 minutes, and they used to convey a new information succinctly to many people at the same time. Conversation – is a method of verbal discussion of the material that is studied – the most common in education. Its task is, firstly, to update knowledge which is known by students (pupils) through targeted and skillfully put questions, and secondly, to achieve the assimilation of new knowledge by them through independent reasoning, generalizations and other mental operations. [13]

The presenter can use intellectual workout. This technique can be used to guide participants in an active «start» condition by the way of updating their knowledge, exchanging ideas, processing common positions and forming motivation to educational and cognitive activities [18].

2. The training exercise.

An important component of each block of the author's program is a set of training exercises, which involves providing psychological conditions that activate the creative and cognitive activity of students (pupils).

It is important to take into account a *basic steps*:

1) a clear definition of the problem or topic for discussion; 2) the choice of who will lead the discussion and encourage the emergence of new ideas; 3) to increase new ideas it may announce a break after a few minutes and then start again; 4) the rules of conduct are: - any criticism;

– borrowing other ideas are not bad;

– a large number of ideas;

5) to improve the quality of ideas, perhaps at the beginning to give to the participants a time to write down their ideas individually;

6) presenting of ideas is cyclically when every members or groups talk about the same idea by turns and ideas are not repeated;

7) the discussion can be conducted in two groups – then each group expands the list which is based on the ideas of the previous group. A changing of the environment can increase the emergence of the new ideas. [21]

The exercises may include using of art therapy products which based on art and creativity.

3. Business game.

This is a method of finding solutions in the conditional problem situation. The elements of the business game: distribution of the roles, competitions, special rules, etc. The business game is used as a method of active teaching of its members with aim to develop their skills in decision-making in a variety of educational situations.

4. Topic «Do you know that? ...» Engages students (pupils) studying issues of tolerance, introduces the interesting life cases. It's formed an integral part of the vision of yourself environment, increased level of tolerance.

Psychological, educational and training facilities development and individual development of tolerance

Consider the content of the lessons of the program.

Lesson 1. «What is tolerance?»

The goal: to create the psychological conditions for understanding the meaning of tolerance, to motivate students (pupils) to exercise tolerance.

Time Required: Depending on the teaching situation.

Materials: paper, pencil or pen, blackboard, chalk.

Introduction by the presenter.

The development and adoption of the rules.

Estimated rules: each participant expresses his own opinion, gives examples from their own experience.

Waiting members on paper, participants write their expectations from the training, read out and affix the poster or expectations write on the board.

The principles of successful classes: active members; motivation for creative activities; creativity; continuous feedback; enhance the position of research participants; optimization of cognitive processes; partner communication.

Mini-lecture on the theme «Tolerance»

The parable of the elders' Dies at one aksakal old village. They came to say goodbye to his people, and say, «Tell us, a wise old man, how could you create such an order in the family, all the sons and daughters in law, daughter in-law and live together in peace?» Can't we say old – serves him paper, pencil, and he kept writing. When dropped from the hands of a dying leaf, all very surprised - it was written 100 times in one word – tolerance!» [9].

Exercise «Tolerance and personal development»

I. Answer the question:

1. How do you understand the meaning of tolerance?
2. What are the main factors that motivate you to exercise tolerance.
3. Is it exist a need for students (pupils) to feel their personal responsibility?
4. Do you consider yourself a tolerant person?
5. Give some examples where tolerance should not exercise.

II. *The game «Associative flower» (pic. 1.)* Try to fill an associative tolerance flower. Tell the trait inherent tolerant person. Students (pupils) paint a flower, in turn, called the trait and go record it.

Pic. 1. *Associative flower*

III. *The Varteha's test (pic. 2)*. By test – German psychologist Eric Vartehh. The test is a sheet of A4, thick black lines divided into 8 equal squares. Each square contains a fixed image you want to continue. You can make yourself form for test printing this table A4:

Pic. 2. *The Varteha's test*

Objective: To continue drawing in each square so that it went over the picture. You can fill squares in any order and using different colors.

Interpretation of Vartehha's test

When interpreting Vartehha's test including aspects:

- semantic content of the picture;
- Features graphics (pressure, shading, location);
- how to fill the squares.

A figure in each square activates certain aspect of personality that is unconscious symbol for a certain part of the psyche. Squares numbers 1, 2, 7 and 8 – are the emotional reaction, the world of feelings. Usually lived here is: Nature, people, animals.

Squares number 3, 4, 5 and 6 – a rational response, the world of logic. Usually there are inanimate objects created by man. If you notice deviations from this rule – look at this square (topic) problem.

Square №1: symbolically marks the beginning point, and in this case – himself, that of himself and his place in the world.

Square №2: wavy line – a germ, and the space around – the human world. Thus, this box shows the relationship with others.

Square №3: three uplink symbolize growth and development. In this case they reflect the motivations and plans for the future ambitions.

Square №4: black square – a symbol of danger, fear and guilt. This box will show the attitude to life's obstacles, dangers, difficulties and psychological burdens that carries people.

Square №5: two perpendicular lines indicate resistance obstacle. In this picture you can see how a person copes with difficulties or predominant strategy of success or avoid failure. It is assumed that the picture would be sent right up.

Square №6: two opposing lines start going in different directions, but require crossing. In this case, relationships with loved ones: convergence or delete them. It is assumed that the line will be connected to the frame or other integrity.

Square №7: dots symbolize sensitivity, intuition, sensitivity to external and internal stimuli. This figure reflects the sensitivity, tact, sensitivity or, callous.

Square №8: arc - a symbol of harmony and security. In the figure indicates a sense of satisfaction, security, a source of strength. Locked objects – departure at as a defense.

Features graphics:

To evaluate the pressure, you need to turn the picture. Then from the seamy side are clearly visible area of a strong and very weak pressure, these issues cause the most stress when one draws, that is problematic, difficult, but pointed to his determination and fighting spirit. Too weak pressure may indicate uncertainty, weakness, depression in this aspect (square).

The location of the pain on the top of the square indicates excessive self-confidence, exaggerating their capabilities, at the bottom – the uncertainty and impairing the abilities side - dependence and finding support in the center – adequate self-esteem and confidence.

Predominant lines: horizontal – weakness, vertical – determination, shading – anxiety.

Picture Size: very large – show off, a violent emotion, quite small – depression, modesty.

Cigarette output data «lines and dots»:

- draws ignores them, that his picture is not associated with them – focus on himself, his «I» in depth «their world»;

- draws them in his image, but not completely – creativity;
- considers all – concentration on specific, important, significant;
- creates a holistic interesting images – creativity.

Completion squares, people usually start with those squares that he «likes», «light», «clear» of those topics that for him the most urgent and important. And squares that are «not like», «some strange», «difficult» to leave then, that those topics in which she has difficulties [12; 19].

Business game «Volitional efforts and achieve goals»

The goal: to create the psychological conditions for motivation to achieve the goal by using the most strong-willed efforts.

I. Answer the questions, citing examples from his own experience:

1) What willpower you need to make in order to achieve maximum results in the educational process?

2) Freedom and creativity. In your opinion, is the concept of complementary or contradictory?

3) What are volitional effort (if necessary) are necessary for self-development?

4) What volitional qualities required tolerant personality?

II. Art Therapy technique «Path to Success»

Task: Draw (build) path to the goal for his hero with a lot of obstacles. Hero can be very student (student), another person or a fairy tale character. The hero must be a goal – what he overcomes all these difficulties (treasure house, friend)? The path of the hero usually runs through the whole letter, and the more you draw obstacles – the better! When the drawing is complete, it is important to discuss each obstacle: how the hero will be able to overcome it. It is important that the hero himself overcame them (climbing, jumping, sailing, beating) and did not enjoy fabulous ways as if a magic wand or a cap of invisibility. Well, if students (students) will be able to come up with ways to overcome every 2-3 obstacles [12; 19].

Class 3. «Think Positively»

The goal: to create the psychological conditions for understanding the meaning of positive thinking, zmotyvuvaty students (pupils) to exercise tolerance.

Time Required: Depending on the teaching situation.

Materials: paper, pencil or pen, blackboard, chalk.

Introduction by the presenter.

The development and adoption of the rules.

Estimated rules: each participant expresses his own opinion, gives examples from their own experience.

Waiting members on paper, participants write their expectations from the training, read out and affix the poster or expectations write on the board.

The principles of successful classes: active members; motivation for creative activities; creativity; continuous feedback; enhance the position of research participants; optimization of cognitive processes; partner communication.

Exercise «Against conflicts, violence and discrimination»

I. Answer the question:

- 1) What are the main factors that cause conflicts in society.
- 2) What is your attitude to the conflict?
- 3) What are the main factors that contribute to violence in society.
- 4) What are the main factors that contribute to discrimination in society.

II. *Art Therapy exercise «Avoidance of conflicts, violence and discrimination»*. On a sheet of paper students (pupils) have to draw on micro groups conflict, violence, discrimination as «targets» and three factors that they «crash» on scarce parts. Then each micro groups has to prove his drawings.

Summing up.

Exercise «We overcome stereotypes»

Task. Students (students) offers pictures or photos of strangers. Each one has to talk about identity: Who is doing what, whether she had problems with the law, and so on.

Exercise «Warm Up»

Get into pairs. Now I am going to label you a 1 or 2.

If you are a 1, you will receive a drawing. You must describe to Person 2 how to draw it without showing Person 2 the drawing. You are only allowed to speak and may not help in any other way.

If you are a 2, you can only use your left hand, and can not use your right hand for anything. You are not allowed to see the picture and you are not allowed to talk. Try to draw the picture from only listening to Person 1.

- Was this easy or challenging? Who was it easy or challenging for? Why?
- How did it make you feel when you couldn't do the task correctly, or at all?
- Did these people choose to be impaired?

Exercise «Mystery Object»

Without looking, pick an object out of the bag and try to guess what it is. Was this activity difficult?

– Television without Sound. We are going to watch this show for a couple minutes with no sound. What was it like watching television with no sound?

– Blind Walk. Find a partner. One person will close their eyes. The other person will lead them around the room for 3-5 minutes. Walk all around the room. After a little bit of time, you will switch roles and repeat for another 3-5 minutes. Since you were not able to see, did you find yourself more alert?

Summarizing the class 2.

Lesson 3. «Self-regulation and coping action»

The goal: to create the psychological conditions for understanding the meaning of self-regulation and coping actions to motivate students (pupils) to exercise tolerance.

Time Required: Depending on the teaching situation.

Materials: paper, pencil or pen, blackboard, chalk.

Introduction by the presenter.

The development and adoption of the rules.

Estimated rules: each participant expresses his own opinion, gives examples from their own experience.

Waiting members on paper, participants write their expectations from the training, read out and affix the poster or expectations write on the board.

The principles of successful classes: active members; motivation for creative activities; creativity; continuous feedback; enhance the position of research participants; optimization of cognitive processes; partner communication.

Mini-lecture «Self-regulation and coping action»

Self-regulation – is the ability to see the ultimate goal of human activity, independently finding the best ways to achieve it and ensure implementation. The result is a self-training focus, organization, skill mastery. Self-regulation has a structure common to all activities and consists of the following components: the purpose of the model relevant conditions, a program of action, evaluation and correction. Self-regulation – the ability to create individual work program and on this basis to control his actions and state. Formation of self-organized training activities disciple equips skills independently perform tasks ability to study lays the foundation [8; 10].

In conclusion it is worth saying that the creation of a secular tolerant education system is one of the great social task, involving the creation of non-denominational schools, and another element involved a centralised curriculum. In this aspect the collection of essays, political philosophers, lawyers, sociologists, theologians and educators explore the role of state schools in promoting tolerance within 21st century multicultural, religiously pluralistic societies.

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КАПУСТЯН И., ЯЛАНСКАЯ С.

ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ КАК ЦЕННОСТНАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ ПОЛИКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ЛИЧНОСТИ СОВРЕМЕННОГО УЧИТЕЛЯ ГУМАНИТАРНЫХ ДИСЦИПЛИН

В статье говорится о толерантности как составляющей ключевых компетентностей учителя-словесника при подготовке к преподаванию в школе. Приведены практические результаты проведенных семинаров и тренингов, опросов и анкетирования студентов. Выделены основные направления и этапы формирования толерантного отношения к окружающим, охарактеризовано понятие толерантности как в общем смысле (а именно как ослабление или отсутствие возможности и реакции на какой-либо неблагоприятный фактор в результате снижения чувствительности к его воздействию), так и на индивидуальном уровне.

Толерантность как ценность раскрыта через отношение к образу жизни других, их поведению, обычаям, чувствам, идеям, верованиям, как условие стабильности и единства обществ, особенно тех, которые не являются гомогенными ни в религиозном, ни в этническом, ни в других социальных измерениях.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, понимание, эмпатия, ценность.

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TOLERANCE AS A VALUABLE COMPONENT OF THE MULTICULTURAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN TEACHER OF HUMANITIES

The article talks about tolerance as a component of the key competencies of the teacher in preparation for teaching in a modern school. Practical results of conducted seminars and trainings, surveys and questionnaires of students are presented. Singled out the basic directions and stages of tolerance towards others, described the concept of tolerance as in a general sense, namely as a weakening or absence of the possibility of reaction to some unfavorable factors by reducing sensitivity to its effects and the individual level. Tolerance as value is revealed through the attitude to the way of life of others, their behavior, customs, feelings, ideas and beliefs as a condition of stability and unity of societies, especially those that are not homogeneous either in religious, ethnic or other social dimensions.

We analyzed the main idea which is to some parents and teachers the idea that they should encourage their children and pupils to be tolerant may seem as obvious as the idea that they should encourage kindness and considerateness. Indeed, amongst parents and teachers of a liberal persuasion a concern to promote tolerance is likely to occupy a central place in their vision of moral education, for whatever else liberalism embraces, tolerance along with liberty are its central ideals. It may seem hardly worth adding that in a multicultural and multifaith society, tolerance takes on extra importance and becomes what has been called 'a major aim in education'. It is defined that learning to be tolerant and respectful of others is key to being successful in life. Due to the fact that children mimic their parents, tolerance can be easily taught to a child from an extremely early age. Many parents are friends with people from different cultural backgrounds, and an easy way for parents to teach their kids to be tolerant is to learn and share more about the heritage of their friends. Sometimes, simply being educated about the customs, holidays, and beliefs of another person is enough to foster tolerance in a home. A lack of education can lead to stereotyping groups of individuals, and denying the qualities that make them

unique. When a child learns to be open-minded about the various cultures, foods, people, and faiths surrounding them, the easier it will be for them to accept others when they get older. In order to prepare children to be open-minded individuals from a young age, there are a few things parents can do to help teach tolerance. First, parents must be careful of what they say around kids because children pick up on negative phrases and slurs almost immediately. This causes a child at school to think that it is okay to repeat hurtful words or comments to someone else because their parents used these words around them. Another important piece of information for parents to keep in mind, is making sure that they teach their children to respect themselves. Often times, a child who lacks self-esteem will treat others badly because they are not confident about themselves. Learning to respect others begins with a respect of one's self, and that is one of the most essential keys to teaching tolerance to a young human being. So the importance of teaching tolerance as a valuable component of the life competence for a modern teacher of Humanities.

Key words: *tolerance, understanding, empathy, value.*

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